

ANALYSIS OF THE STATE OF FINANCIAL AND CREDIT SUPPORT FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF TOURISM IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

Aziza Mahomadrizoevna Karimova

**Senior Lecturer, PhD, Samarkand Institute of Economics and Service,
Uzbekistan**

Abstract. This article discusses issues concerning the assessment of the current state of the tourist market and the procedure for crediting the development of the activities of tourist entities and their provision with a variety of financial and credit resources. The analysis of loans issued by commercial banks of the republic and the analysis of tourist activity of the Samarkand region is carried out.

Keywords: bank, finance, credit, lending, economy, currency, capital, tourism, travel product, tourist, travel market, small enterprises, services, private business

Introduction. The activities of tourism enterprises around the world, in particular in the Republic of Uzbekistan, have changed in recent years, especially after the adoption of the State Program of the country's Socio-Economic Development Strategy for 2017-2021. According to the State Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan for Tourism Development, the influx of foreign tourists to Uzbekistan for 9 months of 2019 amounted to 4.9 million people, which is 26.1% more than in the same period of 2018. However, the number of inflows of foreign tourists under the influence of the coronavirus pandemic in January-July 2020 decreased sharply, and the outflow of tourists from the Republic of Uzbekistan also decreased. As a result, the tourism enterprises of the Republic of Uzbekistan, as well as other countries of the world, have suffered immeasurable losses. To compensate for these losses in the coming years is an urgent problem for all countries of the world.

The assessment of the current state of the tourist market and the procedure for crediting depends on the successful development of the activities of tourist entities and their provision with a variety of financial and credit resources. In the present conditions

of implementation of the priority directions of the State Program of the country's Development Strategy, the credit market becomes more attractive. However, the presence of institutional inequality, a limited set of financial and credit instruments and services used, the lack of effective legal frameworks create problems related to guaranteeing the realization of the property interests of participants in a credit transaction, reduce the effectiveness of tourist services provided and the use of credit resources for the development of tourism enterprises.

The main part. The creation of favorable conditions for the development of financial activities of tourism enterprises, especially for increasing their own financial resources, is important and significant. And not only the tourist business needs financial and credit support (travel agencies, travel agencies, trade, hotels, etc.), but also the citizens themselves need tourist trips. Therefore, consumer demand for lending, for example, to pay for the cost of a trip for the purpose of a tourist trip during a vacation, is also important. Therefore, the formation of financial and credit relations to solve this issue also plays an important role in solving social problems.

Next, let's look at the analysis of loans issued by commercial banks by economic sectors (see: Table 1)

Loans from commercial banks by economic sectors 2017-2019 [1]

Indicator name	January 1, 2017		January 1, 2018		growth % 2017-2018	January 1, 2019		growth % 2018-2019
	billion sum % of total		billion sum % of total	billion sum % of total				
Total credits	52 611	100	110 572	100	110,2	167 391	100	51,4
Industry	18 347	34,9	45 223	40,9	146,5	66 690	39,8	47,5
Agricultural industry	3 033	5,8	4 742	4,3	56,3	9 422	5,6	98,7
Construction	2 218	4,2	3 424	3,1	54,4	5 880	3,5	71,7
Trade and catering	4 072	7,7	5 246	4,7	28,8	10 786	6,4	105,6
Transport and communications	7 149	13,6	16 205	14,7	126,7	20 913	12,5	29,1
Logistics of deliveries and sales	652	1,2	472	0,4	-27,5	2 746	1,6	481,6
Housing and communal services	456	0,9	996	0,9	118,5	1 821	1,1	82,9
Individuals	9 379	17,8	13 600	12,3	45,0	24 427	14,6	79,6
Other sectors	7 304	13,9	20 665	18,7	182,9	24 705	14,8	19,6

The analysis of the annual reports of the Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2017-2019 in the report on loans issued by commercial banks by economic sectors, Table 1, indicates the absence of a sector specifically related to tourism, and loans issued for the tourism sector belong to the "other sectors" sector, on the basis of which it is problematic to conduct an accurate analysis of loans for tourism.

Today, most of the subjects of the sphere need credit support, and the demand for lending to tourism entities is growing every day. However, only a small part of the subjects decide to take out a loan, as they face many problems that are an obstacle to lending.

Despite the fact that such a question was under the close attention of economic scientists [2,3], in practice, credit support for economic entities was implemented within the framework of developed bank lending programs, that is, depending on the specifics of the program and the goals of the financial capabilities of banks.

Based on the data given in Fig.1. it can be concluded that the % loan rate for legal entities is very high, ranging from 22% and above. The same situation can be seen in other banks of the region, the interest rate of which is even higher. An important role is played by the security of the loan, which is required from the borrower. Consequently, the obstacles faced by most of the bank's customers, including tourist enterprises, hotels are not only a high % rate, but also collateral, since many do not have collateral or securities, there is no guarantee of a third party, insurance policy, etc. I.e., these factors are already an obstacle to obtaining a loan, which repel both individuals and legal entities.

To develop methodological and analytical approaches to the processes of identifying the main properties and conditions of granting a loan for investment projects of tourist enterprises in a particular territory, it is necessary to solve such tasks as:

substantiation of the conceptual foundations of innovation and investment development of tourism enterprises, formation of sources and conditions for crediting innovation and investment facilities,

оценка assessment of innovation and investment potential and their attractiveness in a particular territory,

determining the directions of effective use of internal reserves in order to invest in certain areas of activity of tourist enterprises.

So, after analyzing the results of a survey conducted among tourists when visiting various objects of the city of Samarkand based on Fig.3, we found that during their stay in Samarkand, tourists visit the following cultural objects: 28.0% of tourists visited museums, galleries, theaters, exhibitions and art centers; 93% of cultural heritage sites, that is, cultural and historical monuments; 27.0% festive events; 1% nightclubs, 1%

show programs, contests; 23% shopping centers, shops, markets; 5% - ecotourism objects, reserves, reservoirs, mountains; 3% - other/other objects.

Based on Table 2, it can be concluded that tourists could not spend 33.89 thousand rubles for one reason or another. \$US. And based on the data given in Fig.4, special attention is drawn to the fact that it is those objects on which a tourist can spend more money, visiting them is not sufficient. This is a big loss for the domestic service sector and manufacturers of consumer goods. The reason is that business entities have not been able to attract tourists to various services. And the reason for the lack of sufficient attractiveness of the objects is the lack of financial resources for their development.

The opposite phenomenon occurs with our citizens who are going to travel on a tourist trip abroad. It is not surprising that of the total funds taken away by domestic citizens, 5.6% were for food expenses, 12.3% - for food and more than 78% - for the purchase of goods. Unspent funds amount to no more than 2-3%.[5]

Today, the gap between tourism products, financial, commodity and transport markets has slightly increased, as a result of which the second and third lose direct connection with the first. The share serving tourist enterprises accounts for no more than 7-8% of the total volume of services provided to tourists after arrival at the place of tourist travel. All the capital brought by tourists to the place of travel is in "free floating" and has no real material replenishment.

The analysis of the data of the State Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan for the Development of Tourism, the influx of foreign tourists to Uzbekistan for 9 months of 2019 amounted to 4.9 million people, which is 26.1% more than in the same period of 2018.[8] But the number of inflows of foreign tourists under the influence of the coronavirus pandemic as of November 2020 has sharply decreased, and the outflow of tourists from the Republic of Uzbekistan has also decreased. Tourism, like many sectors of the economy, has become one of the sectors that have suffered from the

negative impact of the coronavirus pandemic. Due to the situation of which the number of tourists visiting Samarkand has sharply decreased worldwide, as well as the export of travel services. To compensate for these losses in the coming years is an urgent problem for all countries of the world. Which leads to additional financial and credit support for travel companies during the coronavirus pandemic.

After analyzing the issuance of loans for tourism enterprises, we found that from the commercial banks of Samarkand, the number of loans issued for the tourism sector is very small. Not a significant number of subjects can get a preferential loan, and not many even units decide to take a loan at the price of a commercial loan, since the % rates of the latter are very high. In this connection, entrepreneurs have difficulties with their payments, on the basis of which entrepreneurs of tourist enterprises try not to borrow from the bank.

Today, bank lending to tourism entities is a rather complex and multifaceted process that requires high professionalism from banking institutions. However, most bank employees are completely ignorant of the specifics of tourism activities and apply approaches to tourism entities that are suitable, at best, for trade, or even for investment projects in the construction of new entities for tourists.

So, the resource and organizational limitations of tourism enterprises require the attraction of borrowed capital. This allows them to rely only on a commercial loan, which may include additional conditions for securing the loan (collateral, surety agreement). Taking into account the fact that this group of tourist enterprises most often includes travel agents who do not produce tourist products and do not have the ability to influence the demand for tourist services, it is quite difficult to ensure that tourist enterprises fulfill their obligations to the bank on a commercial loan in a timely manner. The task of tourism enterprises is not just to achieve a specific advantage, but at each stage of activity to provide a stable advantage with the help of credit support, allowing

them to adapt to changes in the market environment, but also to achieve success in the tourist market.

Thus, the development of tourism infrastructure within the framework of the international model is necessary to create favorable conditions for financial and credit support for the activities of tourism enterprises.

Conclusion. After analyzing the sources of financial and credit support and tourism activities in the Samarkand region, we came to the conclusion that financial institutions can have access to financial resources and satisfy the desires of consumers. That is, the need for additional financial resources, and needs can be met with the help of banking services, i.e. loans. At the same time, it should also be taken into account: the more the population attracts a loan for tourist activities, it means that it is necessary to establish preferential loans in order to find an alternative option or access to credit resources.

Having analyzed the loans issued by sectors of the economy, we consider it appropriate to add to the Central Bank's report a sector related to lending specifically to the tourism sector. Also, the analysis and assessment of the current state of the travel services market and the procedure for crediting the tourism sector, we came to the conclusion that the quality and quantity of loans issued, and the organization of business activities in the tourism sector, is not unimportant and the professionalism of the staff. In this regard, there is a need to improve the financial literacy of the staff of both a tourist enterprise and a commercial bank, contributing to an increase in financial results.

References

1. Data from the official website of the Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Annual Report of the Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan 2017, 2018, 2019 (<https://cbu.uz/en/statistics/bankstats>)
2. Jaxongir Z., Aziza K. Financial and Credit Support of the State Tourism Entrepreneurs as a Result Measures Taken to Prevent the Consequences Coronavirus Pandemics in the Reforming New Uzbekistan in the Case of COVID 19 //Annals of the Romanian Society for Cell Biology. - 2021. - p. 6323- 6336-6323-6336.
3. Alieva S.S., Issues of financing of innovative activity of the enterprise. // Biznes-Expert. No. 2019 9 (141) - pp. 94-98.
4. Developed by the author on the basis of data received from commercial banks of the Samarkand region, as of March, 2020.
5. Survey of Samarkand tourists
6. Data of the Department for Tourism Development of the Samarkand region as of January 2020
7. Statistical data of the Department for Tourism Development of the Samarkand region.
8. A brief overview of the main indicators of the tourism market of Uzbekistan for 9 months of 2019.
9. Materials of the banks of Samarkand for the period 2017-2020.